

1 **Aire is expressed in the mammalian Peyer's patch.**

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7 AIRE (autoimmune regulator) expression in the periphery enhances tolerance to self instructed during
8 lymphocyte development in the mTEC. Tolerance to tissue-restricted antigen is mechanistically
9 maintained and executed through localization of Aire expression to the mTEC where negative selection
10 occurs to prevent autoimmunity. We hypothesized tolerance to microbiota occurred at least in part through
11 a mechanism by which the gut microbiota is tolerated at the intestinal epithelial gut mucosa through
12 induction of Aire in the Peyer's Patch (gut associated lymphoid tissue), to facilitate immunologic training at
13 a peripheral site through enabling co-localization of lymphocytes and Aire expression in a secondary
14 lymphoid organ with a "tissue-restricted antigen". We describe here *AIRE* expression in the mammalian
15 Peyer's Patch.
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